

Foreign Language Learning Strategy Use & Gender: The Case of Birzeit University Students*

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Abstract

The current study aimed at investigating the use of foreign language learning strategies among 178 students at Birzeit University enrolled in the English Communication course of B2, 2203. Besides, the study examined the relationship between participants' gender and their foreign language learning strategy use. Oxford's taxonomy for language learning strategies (1990) was utilized. In this taxonomy, language learning strategies are classified into the following six main categories: cognitive, memory, metacognitive, compensation, social and affective- strategies. A questionnaire comprising Oxford's taxonomy for second language learning strategies (1990) was used as an instrument for surveying the language learning strategies.. The overall strategy used by the whole sample was found to be located in the medium range of strategies used. While metacognitive strategies were reported as the most utilized strategies by the participants. Affective strategies registered the lowest use by them. The results of the t-test indicated no statistically significant difference in the participants' use of different learning approaches with respect to the gender variable. Conclusions and pedagogical implications of the results were discussed.

Keywords: Foreign Language Learning Strategies, Gender, Birzeit University.

استخدام استراتيجيات تعلم اللغة الأجنبية وارتباطها بالنوع الاجتماعي لدى طلبة جامعة بيرزيت

ملخص:

هدفت هذه الدراسة إلى استقصاء استراتيجيات تعلم اللغة الانجليزية كلغة أجنبية لدى 178 طالب وطالبة من طلبة جامعة بيرزيت المسجلين في المساق الاجباري (لغة انجليزية - مستوى متقدم). إلى جانب ذلك، هدفت الدراسة إلى تقصي العلاقة بين النوع الاجتماعي الطلبة وطبيعة استراتيجيات التعلم التي يوظفونها في تعلمهم للغة الأجنبية. وقد تم تبني تصنيف اوكسفورد لاستراتيجيات التعلم (1990) في هذه الدراسة حيث

تصنف استراتيجيات التعلم في ستة فئات رئيسية، هي: التذكر والمعرفية والتعويضية وما وراء المعرفية والاجتماعية والعاطفية. وقد تم اعتماد استبانة تشتمل على التصنيف المذكور كأداة الدراسة في جمع البيانات. وقد أظهرت النتائج أن الاستخدام الكلي لاستراتيجيات التعلم لدى عينة الدراسة يقع ضمن المستوى المتوسط. في حين سجلت الاستراتيجيات ما وراء المعرفية الاستخدام الأكبر لدى الطلبة فقد سجلت الاستراتيجيات العاطفية الاستخدام الأدنى. وإلى جانب ذلك، فقد أظهرت نتائج اختبار t-test عدم وجود تباين في استخدام الطلبة لاستراتيجيات التعلم المختلفة وعامل النوع الاجتماعي. وقد تضمن البحث نقاشاً للنتائج وطرحاً لبعض التطبيقات العملية.

كلمات مفتاحية: استراتيجيات تعلم اللغة الأجنبية، النوع

الاجتماعي، جامعة بيرزيت.

Introduction

Education has changed its focus from teachers and textbook materials to focus more on the learners. Consequently, researchers and linguists stopped thinking of language learners as passive recipients. Such developments triggered researchers in the field of second language learning to investigate the different learning strategies that learners use when learning a second language. Researchers in this field have also become interested in tracing many factors that affect the use of these strategies. From the observations of researchers who are language instructors at Birzeit University (BZU), it can be assumed that language learning strategy use is among the main elements of how well students master the foreign language. As Griffiths (2004) states, "Language learning strategies, although still fuzzily defined and controversially classified, are increasingly attracting the interest of contemporary educators because of their potential to enhance learning" (p.5). This study is expected to enrich the research library in this field. Besides, it aimed at investigating the relationship between students' gender, on one hand, and their use of second language learning strategies, on the other hand.

Questions of the study

1. What is the frequency of language learning strategy use by the study participants?

2. Is there a relationship between language learning strategy use by the participants and their gender?

Significance of the study

Two main factors contributed to the significance of the current study. The first factor was an attempt to enrich the existing body of research in the area of foreign language learning strategies. Also, this study is considered an endeavour to help teachers at the Department of Languages and Translation at BZU predict one of the factors that may result in the different achievement levels of their students. Results of the current study are expected to enhance the improvement of students' English language skills through courses provided by the Department.

Methodology

The current study population consists of EFL students at BZU. The sample of the study comprises 178 BZU students registered in the English Communication courses of B2, 2203. To achieve its goals, the study developed a questionnaire as an instrument for surveying the second language learning strategies used in the courses by the subjects of the study. The questionnaire comprises Rebecca Oxford's strategy inventory for language learning (SILL) (1990). Oxford (1990) inventory is a kind of self-report questionnaire that has been used widely by researchers. Furthermore, its reliability has been checked in several ways, and its validity was proven (Oxford, 1996).

These strategies were classified into the following six main categories: cognitive, memory, metacognitive, compensation, affective and social strategies. Hence, the questionnaire comprises a group of items classified into these categories. Participants of the current study were asked to report their responses on a three-point scale, as follows: 1 = Never or almost never true of me, 2 = Somewhat true of me and 3 = Always or almost always true of me. Analysis of the results, item by item, using the SPSS was carried out (See Appendix1). Descriptive statistics (including means, frequency and standard deviations) were calculated to identify the variety of strategies used by the sample. Also, the analysis is meant to

investigate whether there is a relationship between participants' gender and their use of language learning strategy. To achieve this objective the independent sample t-test was carried out.

Literature review

It is widely believed that the beginning of research on language learning strategies dates back to the 1960s which witnessed the development of cognitive psychology. Prior to its development, research on foreign language learning was geared towards teaching methodologies and strategies. Learners were always perceived as passive recipients, and this explains why most of the research focused on the teaching not the learning aspect of foreign languages (Hismanoglu, 2000).

Movement towards a more cognitive view of second language acquisition had its impact on the research in the field of second language learning strategies. The learner started to be observed as an active organizer of received information. While different factors could be thought of as playing a role in language learning, cognitive system started to be thought of as chief to processing. As a result, learning strategies were said to have the greater influence on the rate and level of second language acquisition (Chamot & O'Mally, 1995).

It is widely believed among researchers that the cognitive theory created a justification for using learning strategies and triggered the research related to them. Moreover, this theory helped with the emergence of various definitions and classification models of these strategies (Hismanoglu, 2000). The following sections explore these definitions and classification models.

Defining

Second Language Learning Strategies

Many researchers attempted to define language learning strategies. Each viewed it through his/her own lenses. Rubin (1987) defined language learning strategies as strategies that help in the construction of the language system which the learner build and in turn affect learning directly. As for O'Mally and Chamot (1990), language learning strategies are certain thoughts or behaviours that learners utilize to help them

understand, learn, or recall new information (As cited in Al-Shboul et al., 2010).

Classifying Language Learning Strategies

Various attempts were made by different researchers to categorize language learning strategies. These categorization models came as a result of different observations. Oxford is among those researchers. She derived her model from different sources (Chamot, 2004). Her classification model was claimed to be more comprehensive and detailed than other models. Therefore, Oxford's (1990) taxonomy of language learning strategies was adopted in the present study.

Oxford (1990) classified language learning strategies into six main categories: memory, cognitive, compensation, metacognitive, affective and social strategies. According to her, memory strategies, such as creating mental connections and employing actions, are used for storing and regaining new information. Cognitive strategies, such as analyzing and reasoning, are used for creating and reviewing internal mental modes, in addition to receiving and producing messages in the target language. Compensation strategies allow learners to make up for gaps in their knowledge and skills, by, for example, guessing meanings and using gestures. Metacognitive strategies allow learners to plan, coordinate, and evaluate their own learning. As for affective strategies, they refer to students' feelings while learning. Social strategies involve learning by interaction with others (Griffiths, 2004).

Factors Influencing Foreign Language Learning Strategy Use

Researchers in the field of language learning strategies also became interested in tracing the many factors that affect the use of these strategies. Through their investigation, researchers came up with a long list of nominated factors. Oxford (1989) listed the following: language being learned; time span; degree of consciousness; age; gender; affective variables such as attitudes, enthusiasm, language learning goals, motivational orientation; personality characteristics and general personality type; learning style; aptitude; career orientation; national origin; language teaching

styles; and task requirements (Oxford & Crookall, 1989).

Various studies attempted to investigate the factors that affect the use of foreign language learning strategies. Saricoban and Saricaoglu (2008) examined the effect of variables like gender, age and department. Analysis of data revealed the following: there was a positive relationship between the students' age and the use of affective strategies, while no significant relationship was found between the age, department and gender of the students and the other language learning strategies.

Some researchers conducted methodologically different studies. Instead of studying the effect of identified factors, they tried to identify the general contextual factors that may affect strategy use. In his study, Wu (2008) aimed at identifying the contextual factors influencing the use of language learning strategies of adolescent Chinese ESL learners in Hong Kong. Three contextual factors were found to play role in strategy use. These were: the role of English in Hong Kong, the educational system, and Confucianism, in addition to some learner characteristics.

In his study, Lee Kyung Ok (2003) investigated the use of language learning strategies among 325 Korean secondary school students of English as a foreign language, 163 boys and 162 girls. Results of the study confirmed that girls showed more frequent use of language learning strategies than boys. High-proficiency students registered a higher use of all the strategies than their low-proficiency counterparts. Also, third-year students were found to resort to memory and compensation strategies more than others.

Abu Radwan (2011) was also among the researchers who tried to investigate the relationship between the use of language learning strategies and gender and English proficiency. He examined the use of language learning strategies of 128 English major students at Sultan Qaboos University in Oman. Results showed that the students used metacognitive strategies the most and memory strategies the least. Male participants registered higher use of social and not mental strategies than

females. Besides, results revealed that more proficient students used more cognitive, metacognitive and affective strategies than less proficient ones.

Similarly, Oxford and Lee (2008) tried to examine the effect of the following variables on strategy use: (a) gender, (b) major, (c) education level, (d) English-learning self-image, (e) importance of English, and (f) strategy awareness. The strategy inventory for language learning (SILL) designed by Oxford (1990) was chosen as the instrument to gather the intended data. New qualitative items were also added to the SILL. More than 1,000 students, ranging from middle school to university students, made up the sample of the study. Results of the study came as follow: women used strategies more often than men, and students majoring in humanities, more often than those majoring in science/engineering. Besides, strategy use was higher for the following groups than for the other groups: university students, students who rated their proficiency as excellent, students who considered English to be important and students who were typically aware of strategies.

Yang (2007) conducted a study with the aim of identifying the language learning strategies employed by EFL nursing students in Taiwan from various cultural backgrounds and the effect of language proficiency on language learning strategy use. Oxford's (1990) Inventory for language learning was the research instrument. Results showed that the subjects employed compensation strategies the most. Besides, it was confirmed that language proficiency and ethnicity have effects on students' strategy use.

In his study, Yaping (2010) investigated the use of language learning strategies among 150 students from three different grades in a senior high school in Zhejiang province in China using Oxford's (1990) inventory. Results of the study showed that the participants used learning strategies at a medium level. Gender was found to be strongly correlated only with cognitive and compensation strategies' use. As for the differences among the students in the three grades, the results revealed that Grade 1 students were found to be using strategies a bit more than other graders.

Hashemi (2011) was among the researchers who tried to investigate the effect of gender on the use of second language learning strategies. He examined the use of these strategies among all students of English language at Islamic Azad University of Toyserkan, where the study sample comprised 87 females and 63 males. The subjects of the study reported using cognitive strategies more than other strategies. The results obtained confirmed that the use of some strategies was influenced by the gender variable. Particularly, females registered more preference for using compensation strategies than males.

Similarly, in her study, Abu Shmais (2003) examined the language learning strategies used by Arab males and females EFL majors at an-Najah University in Palestine. The results showed that gender has no significant impact on the use of learning strategies.

Results & Discussion

In this section, results pertaining to the different themes addressed by the below mentioned research questions will be displayed respectively. This section is also concerned with finding interpretations and justifications.

Overall Strategy Use

The following table displays results pertaining to participants' use of individual strategy groups and overall strategy use.

Table (1):
Means, standard deviations and percentages for single strategy groups and overall strategy use

Strategies	Mean	%	StD
Metacognitive Strategies	1.14	57.0	0.37
Cognitive strategies	1.12	56.0	0.28
Compensation strategies	1.11	55.5	0.34
Social Strategies	1.01	50.5	0.39
Memory Strategies	0.90	45.0	0.28
Affective Strategies	0.81	40.5	0.36
Total	1.03	51.5	0.21

Descriptive statistics including mean scores and frequencies for the entire SILL were calculated. According to these results, BZU

students were found to be using foreign language learning strategies in the medium level reflected through the total percentage (51.5%). This might be referred to factors like students' lack of motivation and desire to learn and improve. Lack of foundation background and bad design of curricula could be also elected as expected factors.

The medium use of strategies by participants might also suggest that students in the current study are not fully aware of the range of learning strategies that could be employed while learning a foreign language. Raising students awareness about these strategies should be a priority because of their crucial role in guaranteeing success in learning. It is the task of the language teacher to introduce different learning strategies while teaching. Explicit strategy training by teachers could be a prolific solution. An interactive and engaging learning environment that takes into consideration individual variations and suggests probably useful strategies is necessary. Learners should be helped to identify the type of strategies they already use, to link them to their preferable learning styles and to pick new strategies that might go in harmony with their learning styles and identified strategies. Also, textbooks should be revised so as to integrate more language learning strategies in the different exercises.

Frequencies and means for individual strategy groups were also calculated. Table (1) above shows them in the descending order. As displayed, Metacognitive strategies (57%) were found to be used with the highest frequency by the study participants when compared with the other strategy groups. The cognitive strategies group

came second in rank with a frequency of (56%). Compensation strategies ranked third with a frequency of (55%) followed by social strategies with a frequency of (50%). Both memory and affective strategy groups registered the least with frequencies of (45%) and (40.5%), respectively.

Metacognitive strategies help learners to plan, coordinate and evaluate their learning. BZU students' preference for such strategies suggests that they are successful learners, hard workers and concerned about improving their language.

The low preference which was reported for memory strategies (45%) is surprising. Participants of the current study are thought of as outcomes of a traditional educational system that considers memorization a requirement for successful learning. This may suggest that either the educational system in the Palestinian schools is not traditional as always thought of to be or that participants in the current study are aware that memorization is not the preferred tool when it comes to language learning.

Moreover, participants of the current study registered the lowest frequency of use for affective strategies (40.5). Learners of a foreign language employ such strategies to reflect on their emotional state and feelings during the learning process. This could be referred to as cultural reasons. The Palestinians just as the Arabs are not used to expressing their feelings in public. Such an action might be considered a sign of weakness or lack of confidence. Therefore, English language teachers at BZU should try to have an influence over the emotional atmosphere of their classrooms.

**Table (2):
Means, standard deviations and percentages for single items**

No.	Statement	Mean	%	StD	Rank
A.1	I think of the relationships between what I already know and new things I learn in English.	1.55	77.5	0.49	1
A.2	I use new English words in a sentence so I can remember them.	1.19	59.5	0.57	2
A.3	I connect the sound of a new English word and an image or picture of the word to help me remember the word.	1.04	52.0	0.66	5
A.4	I remember an English word by making a mental picture in which the word can be used.	1.17	58.5	0.76	3
A.5	I use rhymes to remember new English words.	1.11	55.5	0.67	4

No.	Statement	Mean	%	StD	Rank
A.6	I use flashcards to remember new English words.	0.80	40.0	0.72	6
A.7	I physically act out new English words.	0.28	14.0	0.54	9
A.8	I review English lessons often.	0.77	38.5	0.66	7
A.9	I remember new English words or phrases by remembering their location on the page, on the board, or on a street sign.	0.69	34.5	0.69	8
Average (Memory Strategies)		0.90	45.0	0.28	Fifth
B.10	I say or write new English words several times.	1.01	50.5	0.69	11
B.11	I try to talk like native English speakers.	1.25	62.5	0.67	4
B.12	I practice the sounds of English.	1.05	52.5	0.66	8
B.13	I use the English words I know in different ways.	1.29	64.5	0.64	3
B.14	I start conversations in English.	1.13	56.5	0.76	6
B.15	I watch English language TV shows spoken in English or go to movies spoken in English.	1.56	78.0	0.66	1
B.16	I read for pleasure in English.	1.08	54.0	0.71	7
B.17	I write notes, messages, letters, or reports in English.	1.34	67.0	0.71	2
B.18	I first skim an English passage (read over the passage quickly) then go back and read carefully.	1.16	58.0	0.69	5
B.19	I look for words in my own language that are similar to new words in English.	1.02	51.0	0.76	10
B.20	I try to find patterns in English.	0.78	39.0	0.64	14
B.21	I find the meaning of an English word by dividing it into parts that I understand.	1.05	52.5	0.69	8
B.22	I try not to translate word-for-word.	1.00	50.0	0.71	12
B.23	I make summaries of information that I hear or read in English.	0.85	42.5	0.74	13
Average (Cognitive Strategies)		1.12	56.0	0.28	Second
C.24	To understand unfamiliar English words, I make guesses.	1.16	58.0	0.71	2
C.25	When I can't think of a word during a conversation in English, I use gestures.	1.05	52.5	0.64	5
C.26	I make up new words if I do not know the right ones in English.	0.91	54.5	0.74	6
C.27	I read English without looking up every new word.	1.06	53.0	0.62	4
C.28	I try to guess what the other person will say next in English.	1.14	57.0	0.72	3
C.29	If I can't think of an English word, I use a word or phrase that means the same thing.	1.33	66.5	0.72	1
Average (Compensation Strategies)		1.11	55.5	0.34	Third
D.30	I try to find as many ways as I can to use my English.	1.27	63.5	0.68	4
D.31	I notice my English mistakes and use that information to help me do better.	1.30	65.0	0.73	3
D.32	I pay attention when someone is speaking English.	1.38	69.0	0.71	1
D.33	I try to find out how to be a better learner of	1.38	69.0	0.64	1

No.	Statement	Mean	%	StD	Rank
	English.				
D.34	I plan my schedule so I will have enough time to study English.	0.70	35.0	0.67	9
D.35	I look for people I can talk to in English.	0.97	48.5	0.76	7
D.36	I look for opportunities to read as much as possible in English.	0.89	44.5	0.69	8
D.37	I have clear goals for improving my English skills.	1.19	59.5	0.72	5
D.38	I think about my progress in learning English.	1.14	57.0	0.70	6
	Average (Metacognitive Strategies)	1.14	57.0	0.37	First
E.39	I try to relax whenever I feel afraid of using English.	0.86	43.0	0.70	2
E.40	I encourage myself to speak English even when I am afraid of making a mistake.	1.25	62.5	0.67	1
E.41	I give myself a reward or treat when I do well in English.	0.74	37.0	0.81	4
E.42	I notice if I am tense or nervous when I am studying or using English	0.79	39.5	0.69	3
E.43	I write down my feelings in a language learning diary.	0.65	32.5	0.75	5
E.44	I talk to someone else about how I feel when I am learning English.	0.59	29.5	0.73	6
	Average (Affective Strategies)	0.81	40.5	0.36	Sixth
F.45	If I do not understand something in English, I ask the speaker to slow down or say it again.	1.35	67.5	0.68	1
F.46	I ask English speakers to correct me when I talk.	0.91	45.5	0.76	5
F.47	I practice English with other students.	0.87	43.5	0.72	6
F.48	I ask for help from English speakers.	0.99	49.5	0.72	4
F.49	I ask questions in English.	1.17	58.5	0.67	2
F.50	I try to learn about the culture of English speakers.	1.01	50.5	0.73	3
	Average (Social Strategies)	1.01	50.5	0.39	Forth
	Grand Total of all strategies	1.03	51.5	0.21	

Moreover, the descriptive statistics for single items representing the different strategy groups were calculated. As displayed in Table 2 above, it was found out that participants registered the highest preference for the following items: item 15 which is in the cognitive group (I watch English language TV shows spoken in English or go to movies spoken in English), item 1 in the memory group (I think of the relationship between what I already know and the new trends in English), item 32 (I pay attention when someone is speaking English) and item 33 (I try to find out how to be a

better learner of English). These results point to a strong endeavour on the side of the learners to improve their language and their performance as language learners as clearly stated in item 33.

In contrast and as displayed in the table above, item 7 belonging to the memory group (I physically act out new English words) sharply registered the lowest frequency (14%). This supports the claim that memory strategies are always downgraded and thought of as fruitless. Moreover, participants might feel frustrated from using memory strategies since memorization was

the widely used tool to learn at their previous schools, as commonly thought by people. Item 44 (I talk to someone else about how I feel when I am learning English) comes next with a frequency of 29.5%. This low preference for item 44 (I talk to someone else about how I feel when I am learning English) which belongs to the affective strategies might support the claim that Palestinian people do not prefer to talk about their feelings in front of

others since such an action is always associated with lack of strength and self-esteem.

Strategy use and gender

To answer the second research question concerning the relationship between participants gender and their strategy use, the Independent Sample T-Test was carried out. The table below displays the result

Table 3
Results of Independent Sample t-test

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig.
avg_a	Male	81	0.8601	0.30163	1.871	0.089
	female	97	0.9393	0.26304		
avg_b	Male	81	1.0811	0.29554	1.349	0.408
	female	97	1.1370	0.25664		
avg_c	Male	81	1.1255	0.32546	0.605	0.382
	female	97	1.0945	0.35266		
avg_d	Male	81	1.0823	0.33965	1.801	0.387
	female	97	1.1810	0.38333		
avg_e	Male	81	0.7757	0.35762	1.270	0.953
	female	97	0.8436	0.35340		
avg_f	Male	81	0.9753	0.38740	1.100	0.946
	female	97	1.0412	0.40685		
avg_all	Male	81	0.9975	0.21613	1.889	0.901
	female	97	1.0575	0.20654		

As displayed in the table above, the (t-value = 1.889) was found to be lower than its tabulate value at (sig.=0.901). This confirms that there is no statistically significant difference in students strategy use with reference to their gender. While such results contradicts the results of many studies conducted in the same area (e.g. Yaping (2010); Hashemi (2011); Oxford & Lee (2008)), they still go in harmony with some others (e.g. Abu Shmais (2003); Saricoban Saricaoglu (2008)). In her study, Abu Shmais (2003) examined the language learning strategies used by Arab males and females EFL majors at an-Najah University in Palestine.

The results showed that gender has no significant impact on the use of learning strategies.

In spite of the t-test result confirming that there is no statistically significant difference between male and female participants regarding their language learning strategy use, it should be stated that females slightly surpass their male counterparts in employing almost all the strategy types except for compensation strategies. Most of the research in the addressed area, learning strategies, support this conclusion that females excel males in the amount of learning strategies they utilize when learning a second language. For

example, Oxford and Lee (2008) tried to examine the effect of different variables including gender on strategy use. The results confirmed that women used strategies more extensively than men. Females are claimed to be more proficient in memorizing and retrieving information. They are better than males in monitoring their own performance and reflecting on it.

As for the compensation strategies, results of the current study indicate that males are slightly more capable of searching for alternative ways and methods to improve their learning and to make up for the noticed deficiencies.

However, at the end, it should be noted that the result of the t-test could not be neglected. Such result indicated that there is a need for more research exploring factors affecting students language learning strategy use other than gender. The result also showed that teachers are called to give more attention to factors other than gender when teaching or working on lesson designs and plans.

Conclusions

This study was conducted among 178 BZU students registered in the English Communication course of B2, 2203. The main objective was to investigate their foreign language learning strategy use. Besides, the relationship between the use of the previously mentioned strategies and the variable of gender was examined. Oxford's (1990) Inventory for Foreign Language Learning Strategies constituted the data gathering instrument, while the SPSS was utilized as the data analysis tool. Results of the study confirmed that the subjects were medium-strategy users. The variable of gender was found to have no statistically significant relationship with the students' strategy use. However, some caution remains with regard to such results. They stay limited to BZU students. Thus, it may not be acceptable to generalize these results to all foreign language learners in other foreign language learning settings. More in-depth research is needed to reconsider other learners in different settings and to investigate other factors that may affect learning strategy use like age, motivation, personality characteristics.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the current study, the researcher recommends that English teaching staff at BZU/Department of Languages and Translation need to reconsider their teaching approaches and materials in order to incorporate more learning strategies to meet the students' needs and interests. Students could be made more sophisticated if teachers guarantee their indulgence in an environment rich of input. This could trigger wider use of learning strategies. Students should also be motivated to reflect on their own performance while learning, and keep searching for better ways to enhance their language skills. In other words, students should be more conscious about the wide range of language learning strategies that could foster their learning.

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Appendix 1:

The Questionnaire

Gender:

1) Male

2) Female

Read each sentence carefully in this section. Place an X next to the most appropriate choice. There are no right or wrong answers to the statements. The meaning of each number is as follows:

1. Never or almost never true of me.
2. Somewhat true of me.
3. Always or almost always true of me.

Part A	Never or almost never true of me	Somewhat true of me	Always or almost always true of me
1. I think of relationships between what I already know and the new things I learn in English.			
2. I use new English words in a sentence so I can remember them.			
3. I connect the sound of a new English word and an image or picture of the word to help me remember the word.			
4. I remember an English word by making a mental picture in which the word can be used.			
5. I use rhymes to remember new English words.			
6. I use flashcards to remember new English words.			
7. I physically act out new English words.			
8. I review English lessons often.			
9. I remember new English words or phrases by remembering their location on the page, on the board, or on a street sign.			
10. I say or write new English words several times.			
11. I try to talk like native English speakers.			
12. I practice the sounds of English.			
13. I use the English words I know in different ways.			
14. I start conversations in English.			
15. I watch English language TV shows spoken in English or go to movies spoken in English.			
16. I read for pleasure in English.			

17. I write notes, messages, letters, or reports in English.
18. I first skim an English passage (read over the passage quickly) then go back and read carefully.
19. I look for words in my own language that are similar to new words in English.
20. I try to find patterns in English.
21. I find the meaning of an English word by dividing it into parts that I understand.
22. I try not to translate word-for-word
23. I make summaries of information that I hear or read in English.
-

Part C

24. To understand unfamiliar English words, I make guesses.
25. When I can't think of a word during a conversation in English, I use gestures.
26. I make up new words if I do not know the right ones in English
27. I read English without looking up every new word.
28. I try to guess what the other person will say next in English.
29. If I can't think of an English word, I use a word or phrase that means the same thing
-

Part D

30. I try to find as many ways as I can to use my English.
31. I notice my English mistakes and use that information to help me do better.
32. I pay attention when someone is speaking English.
33. I try to find out how to be a better learner of English.
34. I plan my schedule so I will have enough time to study English.
35. I look for people I can talk to in English.
36. I look for opportunities to read as much as possible in English.
37. I have clear goals for improving my English skills.
38. I think about my progress in learning English.
-

Part E

39. I try to relax whenever I feel afraid of using English.
40. I encourage myself to speak English even when I am afraid of making a mistake.
41. I give myself a reward or treat when I do well in English.

42. I notice if I am tense or nervous when I am studying or using English.

43. I write down my feelings in a language learning diary.

44. I talk to someone else about how I feel when I am learning English.

Part F

45. If I do not understand something in English, I ask the speaker to slow down or say it again.

46. I ask English speakers to correct me when I talk.

47. I practice English with other students.

48. I ask for help from English speakers.

49. I ask questions in English.

50. I try to learn about the culture of English speakers.
